

Developing polygenic risk models with rich full medical profiles

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Our research group has built risk models for several polygenic diseases, including stroke, coronary artery disease, diabetes and some cancer types [1-4] and participated in the development and rollout of genetic risk models to a significant number of participants of Estonian Biobank [5]. However, note that risk models [1-4] that do not utilise genetic information. The main reason is applicability – genotype information is not widely available. The same tradeoff between applicability and precision quality is present even in models that utilise only clinical features. The simplest models use only previous diagnoses to predict disease risk and ignore more complex features. As a result, they have relatively low prediction quality while they can be applied in almost all settings. For instance, such a prediction model for stroke achieves 58% AUC ROC, while models utilising lab measurements achieved over 90% AUC ROC score. Such high precision begs the question of whether the usage of genetic information can significantly improve the prediction quality.

The answer to the question depends on how much clinical information is available for the study cohort. As a concrete example, consider typical disease patterns and their power to predict stroke onset during a year. The figure below shows how much the prevalence in the cluster is higher or lower than the average stroke prevalence in the cohort (lift) and what the sizes of corresponding clusters are. There are a few small clusters with high lift and a handful of large clusters where no relevant diseases are recorded. In such settings, auxiliary information regarding genetic risk scores or lab measurements could significantly improve prediction quality.

In particular, we have studied short-term risk models for stroke. As stroke is potentially recurrent, we need to isolate individual stroke episodes. The latter is a non-trivial task since patients are hospitalised both for acute treatment and intensive rehabilitation. Together with medical doctors, we developed a corresponding segmentation algorithm and validated its performance. This algorithm uses ICD-10 diagnoses to identify ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke episodes. Unfortunately, ICD-10 diagnoses used in clinical practice do not perfectly match the epidemiological stroke classification. Together with medical doctors, we estimated the correctness of our approximate classification by estimating positive prediction values for ischaemic stroke and its TOAST subtypes. Results indicate that ICD-10 codes can be used to identify ischemic stroke episodes, but the data in Estonia's Electronic Health Records is insufficient to distinguish all TOAST subtypes. We plan to publish these findings.

We have also worked on the enrichment of clinical observations. Estonia's Electronic Health Records do not contain structured information about important lifestyle factors such as levels of smoking and alcohol consumption and series of complaints and observations related to circulatory system diseases such as thrombosis and bleeding events and blood pressure measurements. To alleviate this problem, we have developed and refined extraction algorithms for such clinical features. Armed with these results, we have developed several risk models for stroke [2]. Currently, we are studying the reasons for non-transferability of existing prediction models [6] to Estonian data. These results are still in preliminary form, but the final analysis more concretely answers what is the impact of lab measurements compared to genetic risk scores.

References

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